

A comparative study of the effect of precompression on the thermal stability of potassium bromate to ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate

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The effects of precompression on the kinetics of decomposition of three solids, viz. potassium bromate, ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate have been examined by thermogravimetry in air. The rates of decomposition (isothermally) of these solids are found to be significantly modified by precompression. The rate law remains unaltered. Precompression does not affect the basic mechanism of the solids. It could only modify the concentration of potential sites.

The vast knowledge in the properties of solids, such as electronic spectra, thermal and photochemical decomposition, has been a direct consequence of better understanding of the imperfect solid state. Studies have shown that more perfect a crystal, the smaller is its reactivity where there are centres of reactivity in solids¹.

We have investigated the effect of precompression on the thermal decomposition kinetics of three solids, viz. potassium bromate, ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate with a view to bringing out a comparative account of the rate of dislocations (produced by precompression) on these decomposition reactivity of the solids.

The various kinetic equations that describe solid state decomposition may be expressed by the general form,

$$g(\alpha) = kt \quad (1)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is a function of α and is dependent on the mechanism of the decomposition. The rate equation which provides the most satisfactory fit to the experimental α - t data was found out by the method of weighted least-squares. The plot of $g(\alpha)$ [calculated from the experimental values] versus time gave the best linear graph which was acceptable for describing further mechanism.

Values of the correlation coefficient (r) is most often used for the selection $g(\alpha)$ that best describe the experimental results²⁻⁴. From the literature one finds that r is not a good index for selecting the proper $g(\alpha)$ equation³⁻⁵.

Rozycki and Maciejewski⁶ calculated the following value (R),

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_{\text{cal}} - \alpha_{\text{exp}})^2 \quad (2)$$

where α_{cal} and α_{exp} are respectively the calculated and experimental values of α and n is the number of experimental values of α . These authors suggested that the function with minimum R values is selected as the best one for describing the experimental data. In the present investigation, it was noticed that the function which corresponds to the minimum R values also corresponds to the maximum value of r .

Results and Discussion

The isothermal decomposition of unpressed and pressed potassium bromate samples was carried out in the temperature range 663–683 K at five different temperatures. It was found that the initial portion of the fractional decomposition vs time curves corresponding to the fractions of decomposition 0.15–0.50 agrees with contracting cube rate law. Thus, the contracting cube rate constants, k (Tables 1 and 2) were used to estimate the reactivity of the samples.

Table 1 Values of initial rate constants (k) at various temperatures computed using weighted LSM for the initial stage of decomposition of pure KBrO_3 based on contracting cube rate equation

Decomp. temp., K	663	668	673	678	683
$k \times 10, \text{min}^{-1}$	0.969	1.429	3.429	4.523	6.0

Table 2. Values of initial rate constants (k) obtained from weighted LSM for the decomposition of precompressed KBrO_3 at 668 and 678 K, based on contracting cube rate equation

Pelleting press, $P \times 10^3, \text{kg cm}^{-2}$	$k \times 10, \text{min}^{-1}$	
	668 K	678 K
0 (Unpressed)	1.429	4.523
2	1.284	2.434
4	2.027	4.891
6	1.286	2.432
8	0.987	2.571
10	1.103	2.206
12	1.759	2.353
14	1.429	2.083

The weight-loss data of the present study support the findings of Bancroft and Gesser⁷ that the decomposition reaction proceeds according to the equation,

After using fourteen kinetic equations, none of them described the complete decomposition. Some of the earlier workers^{8,9} also reported similar difficulty with potassium bromate decomposition.

When the pressure P is increased it imparts a zig-zag appearance to rate-pressure plot (Fig. 1). The value of activation energy (E) was found to be 215 kJ mol⁻¹ for both unpressed and pressed samples (Fig. 2 and Table 2). Diefallah *et al.*¹⁰ through regression analysis, found that phase-boundary controlled models (i.e. contracting square and contracting cube rate laws) are suitable for describing this decompositions. Several workers^{8,9} reported similar

Fig. 1 Plots for the effect of precompression on the rate of decomposition of (a) KBrO_3 at 668 K, (b) KBrO_3 at 678 K, (c) NH_4ClO_4 at 473 K, (d) KMnO_4 at 513 K.

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plot for the thermal decomposition of KBrO_3 at different temperatures: (x) unpressed, (X) pressed $2 \times 10 \text{ kg cm}^{-2}$, (Δ) $14 \times 10 \text{ kg cm}^{-2}$.

values of activation energy in the temperature range 653–693 K in the same range of fractional decomposition. The activation energy is unaffected by precompression (Fig. 2 and Table 1) and hence the mechanism of the decomposition is not affected by precompression. The pretreatment results in modification of the concentration of the potential sites.

The absence of an induction period in the preliminary graphs of potassium bromate decomposition suggests that it involves instantaneous nucleation phenomenon. When nucleation is rapid over the surface the reaction is controlled by the movement of an interface at constant velocity. We find here that the region of fractional decomposition, 0.15–0.5, is best described by contracting cube law with an activation energy, $E = 215 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

The results of precompression studies of potassium bromate in the present context can be compared with the solids, viz. ammonium perchlorate^{11–13} and potassium permanganate¹⁴ which were already studied by other researchers. But in all cases, the precompressed samples were reported to decompose faster than the uncompressed sample, unlike the potassium bromate system. In this 'not-so-common' behaviour of pressed potassium bromate, we have extended the precompression studies to two more solids, viz. ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate which decompose according to an electron transfer mechanism¹⁴ in contrast to the diffusion mechanism of potassium bromate suggested here.

Thermal decomposition of ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate was subjected to precompression in the range 2–14 tons and kept at 473 and 513 K, respectively. The initial rate of decomposition of ammonium perchlorate was made suitable by using the first order equation in the range of fractional decomposition 0–0.5 whereas the rate of potassium permanganate for the initial acceleratory period at a range of 0.15–0.5, is shown to be agreeing with Prout-Tomkin equation. The rate of decomposition generally increases with the pelleting pressure and becomes steady at high pressure (Fig. 1). This shows that the basic mechanism of decomposition (electron transfer process)^{14–17} remains unaltered by precompression. Since an electron is extremely small, its movement would not affect significantly by densification of solid matrix of ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate. However, densification may play a dominant role in diffusion-controlled reactions of potassium bromate decomposition leading to a decrease in the rate (Fig. 1).

In the case of ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate the rate-enhancing effect on compression was attributed to a result of plastic deformation occurring and consequently the generation of active grain boundaries and dislocations which are seats of high reactivity. The dislocation density increases with increasing pelleting pressure leading to a regular increase in the rate. X-Ray diffraction and infrared studies^{13,15,16} support the above explanation.

The general decrease in the rate of decomposition of precompressed potassium bromate (Fig. 1) is not the only phenomenon of plastic deformation causing an increase in the dislocation density. On compression the change in the rate can also be brought by way of its effect on sintering and densification of solids. When potassium bromate is compressed, it is possible that vacancies get annealed causing great reduction in the open volume and densification of the solid matrix occurs. The diffusion of ions plays a vital role in determining the rate. It appears that a study of the effect of precompression on the thermal decomposition reactivity of a solid is capable of bringing out the mechanism of decomposition in a simple manner.

Experimental

A.R. grade samples (Merck) of potassium bromate, ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate were used. Crystals (106–90 microns) were compressed for about 1 min at varying pressures (2–14 tons) in a hydraulic press (13 mm die, Specac Kent, England). The pellet formed was gently broken and the particle size was again controlled as 106–90 microns. The reactivities of the untreated as well as pretreated samples were measured by decomposing them using TG method. The temperature of the furnace was controlled (± 1 K) by a temperature indicator-controller (Century CT 806T).

Isothermal method¹⁸ was used for studying the decomposition reaction of potassium bromate, ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate. The TG of untreated and precompressed samples of potassium bromate was carried out at five different temperatures (663, 668, 673, 678 and 683 K). A precompressed sample (20 mg) was used for studying the decomposition. The untreated and precompressed samples of ammonium perchlorate and potassium permanganate at decomposition temperatures 473 and 513 K, respectively, were also investigated as a comparison. The extension due to weight of the material was noted. The weight-loss for known intervals was noted from the contraction of the quartz spring (Thermal Syndicate Ltd., U.K.). The reaction was considered to be over when the position of the spring remained constant. Duplicate runs were conducted for all samples and almost the same values were obtained.

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